

Robotic Arm Control for Dice Manipulation using Computer Vision and IMU Sensor

Irene Pippo^{*+}, Alexander Brown^{†+}, Giulio Besi^{‡+} and Lorenzo Liguori^{§+}

^{*}Department of Mechanics, Energetics, Management and Transportation

University of Genoa and ReWing s.r.l., Genoa, Italy (irene.pippo@edu.unige.it)

[†]Department of Electronic and Electrical Engineering

University of Leeds, Leeds, United Kingdom (el19ajb@leeds.ac.uk)

[‡]Department of Engineering Sciences and Methods

University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, Reggio Emilia, Italy (giulio.besi@unimore.it)

[§]Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering

Sapienza University of Rome, Rome, Italy (lorenzo.liguori@uniroma1.it)

Abstract—Being the main element in many games around the world, a dice is considered as easy to be rolled by a human. However, when the task needs to be performed by a robot, specific challenges arise, particularly if the task is to place the dice in space depending on a specific request. In this article, we address the problem of task-dependent dice rolling with a 6-DoF robotic manipulator. This paper is the result of a challenge in which the authors have competed during the 2nd Doctoral Summer School on Robotics and Intelligent Machines - DRIMS2.

Index Terms—Robotic Challenge, DRIMS2, Dice Manipulation

I. INTRODUCTION

This paper presents a multidisciplinary approach showcasing the integration of various technologies to design a functional robotic demo, where a robotic arm has to manipulate a dice depending on a specific task [1], [2]. The work showcased is the winning project of the challenge proposed during the 2nd Doctoral Summer School on Robotics and Intelligent Machines (DRIMS2), where the task was to manipulate a sensor-equipped dice with a commercial robotic arm to display a target number on its uppermost face. The proposed solution involves the integration of mechanical design, utilizing 3D printing for rapid prototyping, sensor integration, vision and control algorithms [3].

II. METHODOLOGIES

The experimental setup provided during this challenge includes: i) the commercial robotic manipulator GoFa (ABB, Switzerland), ii) a sensor-equipped dice to be manipulated, and iii) a fixed OAK-D Pro camera (Luxonis, USA) to detect the pose and upright face of the dice. To complete the task, we propose the following approach: as the dice has an initial unknown orientation (unknown disposition of the lateral faces, due to the top-down view) it is possible to roll the dice 90° around one of the planar axes (either

This work was supported by the 2nd Doctoral Summer School on Robotics and Intelligent Machines - DRIMS2. The DRIMS2 initiative is connected to the national PhD program in Robotics and Intelligent Machines, which has been pioneered within the I-RIM framework <https://drim.i-rim.it/>.

⁺These authors contributed equally to this work.

Fig. 1. Control strategy

X or Y, setting Z as perpendicular to the camera image) to calculate the dice orientation and thus show the target face by performing one single 3D Spherical Linear Interpolation (SLERP). This is completed during the transformation from the initial quaternion position of the dice, detected from the sensors within, and the target orientation. Additionally, the reference position used for the control algorithm is the base frame of the robot, given as a challenge constraint. The control strategy flowchart can be seen in Fig. 1. A framework was built for the solution using Robot Operating System (ROS), as it allows for information to be exchanged between the different modules designed during the sub-tasks of the challenge. Each module (dice, camera, control, robot) acts as a ROS node, with the module directly interacting with the robot controller being the control one. In the following subsections we describe the solutions proposed for each challenge sub-task, divided as: gripper design, communications, interface, vision, control.

A. Gripper design

The first challenge was to design and 3D print the clamps for the end-effector to be integrated on the robot arm, capable of gripping the cube shaped dice (70 mm edge). The mechanical constraints were: i) the shape of the object; ii) the object dimensions, since the opening excursion of the end-effector is fixed, so the designed clamps should ensure the grasp of the

Fig. 2. Dice detection and centroid creation on a frame taken from the camera

provided dice. First, a Computer Aided Design model of the part was designed in Creo Parametric (PTC, USA). This was then 3D printed in Polylactic Acid (PLA) via Fused Deposition Modeling on an Ultimaker S5 (Ultimaker, the Netherlands).

B. Communication interface

The communication part is used as an intermediate between the dice and the control algorithm for the robot to perform the manipulation. Inside the dice is a Particle Argon board, which includes an inertial measurement unit (IMU) used to obtain the dice orientation w.r.t. the world frame. Data from the IMU sensor is received by the PC using an application designed in LabVIEW environment. The data communication between the PC and the IMU is made by User Datagram Protocol using unbuffered mode at a frequency of 100 Hz with a delay of 10 Hz. Using the IMU unit roll, pitch and yaw are computed to obtain the dice orientation in space. The LabVIEW application acts as the node transmitting the roll-pitch-yaw data from the IMU unit to the control node. By knowing how the IMU is placed inside the dice, it is possible to compute the rotation offset between initial and target orientations after firstly rolling the dice of 90° , as described in section II. The designed interface also communicates with the vision node, which sends information about the starting top face.

C. Vision

With a custom vision algorithm, the top face of the dice is detected and the initial pose of its frame is calculated [4]. OpenCV library was used to detect the face-up image and the number of dots. First, after correcting the distortion of the lenses, the algorithm applies a colour mask to detect the region of interest where the face of the dice is located, before a contour detection is performed to find its edges. Having the geometric shape of the face, its centroid is computed such that the information about the location of the centre of gravity on the plane is obtained. This information is crucial to set the picking pose of the robot's gripper. Moreover, with the centroid coordinates it is possible also to obtain the dice's frame orientation using the information received from the IMU, as shown in Fig. 2. Finally, the dots are detected and counted to ensure the detection of the top face is accurate. Everything was then wrapped into a ROS node to communicate with the LabVIEW application and the control node.

D. Control

The control is the core of our approach. As mentioned in section II, the adopted strategy exploits the fixed configuration

Fig. 3. Consecutive phases of the dice manipulation

of the dice and the SLERP interpolation, which states that given initial and final quaternions q_0 , q_1 respectively, the intermediate quaternion q at time t along the shortest path between q_0 and q_1 on the unit hyper-sphere is given by:

$$q(t) = q_0(q_0^{-1}q_1)^t \quad (1)$$

Eq. (1) is used by the trajectory planner to move the robot from initial to target position. The control frequency has been set to 500 Hz as it is the same for GoFa controller. The control pipeline is structured as follows: first, the corresponding quaternion of the initial dice pose is computed. Then the dice is rolled 90 degrees around one of the planar axes: if the new shown face-up is the target one, the control stops and the task is completed; otherwise, the orientation of the dice frame is computed based on the known configuration of the faces. At this point, the rotation angle to apply to the dice frame is computed by means of the 3D SLERP interpolation between the quaternion of the initial face and the quaternion of the target face - respectively q_0 and q_1 in (1). The computed angle is then transformed to be used w.r.t. the robot's base frame to respect the constraints mentioned in section II. After executing the trajectory, the dice is put again on the ground plane, with the target face upwards. Between each method step, there are also safe linear trajectories implemented to avoid any possible collision that may occur between robot and either the ground plane or the camera holding structure. Four consecutive faces of the proposed control strategy can be seen in Fig. 3.

III. CONCLUSION

Multiple engineering disciplines are integrated in this work to successfully accomplish the challenge presented during the 2nd Doctoral Summer School DRIMS2, where the task was to manipulate a sensor-equipped dice with a robotic arm in order to display a desired target face. The winning approach adopted in our project allowed us to achieve the goal in a simple way, minimising the number of procedures while accurately achieving the goal.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. Bohg, A. Morales, T. Asfour, and D. Kragic, "Data-driven grasp synthesis: A survey," *IEEE Transactions on Robotics*, 30(2), 289-309, 2014.
- [2] G. Du, K. Wang, S. Lian, and K. Zhao, "Vision-based robotic grasping from object localization, object pose estimation to grasp estimation for parallel grippers: a review," *Artif Intell Rev* 54, 1677-1734, 2021.
- [3] B. Siciliano, L. Sciavicco, L. Villani, and G. Oriolo, "Robotics: Modelling, planning and control," *Springer*, 2009.
- [4] R. Szeliski, "Computer vision: Algorithms and applications," *Springer*, 2011.